

MATHEMATICS TEACHERS' GENDER, KNOWLEDGE OF SUBJECT MATTER AND IMPLEMENTATION OF EDUCATION LAW IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UYO SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.

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Abstract

This study was to determine the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter and implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools in Uyo Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The Expo facto research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of all all the 346 Mathematics teachers in the public secondary schools, Uyo Senatorial District. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 100 Mathematics teachers for the study. Data was collected using a researcher developed instrument named, Mathematics Teachers' Gender, Knowledge of Subject Matter and Implementation of Education Law Questionnaire (MTGKSMIELQ). The instrument was further subjected to face validity by three experts; two in psychological Foundation and one in Educational Administration and Planning, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics was 0.86. Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics were used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using Independent t-test Statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools. Mathematics Teachers' gender had no significant influence on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools. Recommendations were made among others that government should invest in and promote professional development opportunities for mathematics teachers that are entirely gender-neutral.

Keywords: *Teachers' gender, knowledge of subject matter and implementation of Education Law.*

Introduction

Mathematics education plays a crucial role in developing students' critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and logical reasoning among learners. According to Ekim, Akpan and Dada (2022), It is a determinant of success to all kinds of profession due to its connectivity to many other subjects. Thus, a solid foundation in Mathematics is essential for success in various academic and professional pursuits (Dee, 2017). It therefore behooves that students should develop positive attitude towards the learning of the subject and as such, Mathematics teachers as key facilitators in the learning process should significantly irrespective of their gender, influence the students' understanding and positive attitude toward the subject. Understanding the influence of Mathematics teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter and the implementation of Education Law is essential for several reasons. Firstly, teachers serve as role models, and their gender may impact students' perceptions of the subject. Secondly, variations in subject matter knowledge between male and female teachers may affect teaching methodologies and, consequently, students' learning experiences. Finally, investigating these aspects is crucial for promoting gender equality and ensuring equitable educational outcomes (Hill, Rowan & Ball, 2015).

Gender stereotypes associated with teaching Mathematics often perpetuate societal norms regarding perceived strengths and weaknesses based on gender (Guiso, Monte, Sapienza, & Zingales, 2018). For instance, the stereotype that Mathematics is a "male" subject might influence students' expectations of their teachers, potentially impacting teacher-student interactions and the learning environment. Studies exploring the impact of teacher gender on student outcomes have yielded varied results. Akpan (2015), suggests that gender does not significantly affect student performance, while other studies propose that teacher gender can influence students' engagement, confidence, and interest in Mathematics. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for creating inclusive educational environments.

Teachers' proficiency in the subject matter is fundamental for effective Mathematics instruction. A deep understanding of mathematical concepts enables teachers to convey complex ideas clearly, answer students' questions confidently, and adapt instructional strategies to diverse learning needs

(Holmlund, McNally and Viarengo, 2021). Research by Edet (2019), indicates a positive correlation between teachers' subject matter knowledge and their effectiveness in the classroom. However, gender-specific analyses within these studies are often limited. Investigating the gender dimension in teachers' subject matter knowledge is vital for a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing educational outcomes.

Education laws and policies provide a framework for educational institutions, shaping their structure, curriculum, and practices (Ekanem, 2019). Understanding these laws is essential for educators to ensure compliance and provide quality education. Gender-specific implications within these laws may affect teacher-student dynamics and overall educational experiences. According to Goldin, Katz, and Kuziemko (2016), Challenges in implementing education laws may include issues related to resource allocation, administrative constraints, and resistance to change. Gender-related factors, such as biases in decision-making processes or unequal distribution of opportunities, can compound these challenges. Investigating these issues is crucial for addressing disparities and fostering an inclusive educational environment (James, 2018).

Empirically, Akpan (2015) conducted a study to investigate the influence of Teachers' attributes on their knowledge of subject matter in Delta State, Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The sample was 344 teachers drawn from a population of 86 1829 teachers in public secondary schools in the study area. Data collection was carried out with the use of two research instruments titled "Teachers' Attributes Questionnaire (TAQ)" and "Knowledge of Matter Questionnaire (KMQ)". The reliability of TAQ and KMQ are 0.74 and 0.78 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis (r) was used for data analysis at .05 level of significance. Results obtained revealed that there is a significant influence of teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter. The objective of this present study are the same with that of the previous study.

Obilor (2020) conducted a study to investigate the influence of teachers' demographic variables on implementation of Education Law in senior secondary school in Rivers State. The research design was a descriptive survey with simple random sampling techniques to select a sample of 990 Senior Secondary (SS 2) students from a population of 6420 students in the three Senatorial Districts of Rivers State. Data collected through a researcher – developed, structured questionnaire entitled "Teachers' Demographic

Variables on Implementation of Education Law Questionnaire (TDVIELQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.86, was analyzed with mean, standard deviation and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). While mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, the ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. It was found that teachers' gender influenced implementation of Education Law. The previous study was not conducted in Uyo Senatorial District. Thus, the necessity of this present study.

The above literature reviews revealed that very few studies have been carried out by scholars based on this variable under study and also none to the knowledge of the researcher have been done in Uyo Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. As such, this study become necessary.

Statement of The Problem

Understanding the impact of Mathematics teachers' gender on subject matter knowledge and the implementation of Education Law is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, teachers are influential role models, and their gender may shape students' perceptions of the subject. Secondly, disparities in subject matter knowledge between male and female teachers could impact teaching methodologies, potentially affecting students' learning experiences. Finally, this investigation is vital for promoting gender equality in education, aligning with broader efforts to ensure equitable educational outcomes. Despite the significance of this topic, there are notable gaps in the existing literature. Many studies focus on general teacher effectiveness without specifically addressing gender-related aspects. Limited research explores how gender influences subject matter knowledge and the practical implications of education laws in mathematics education. Addressing these gaps will provide a more nuanced understanding of the dynamics involved and inform targeted interventions to enhance educational equity. Therefore, this study aim to determine the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter and implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools in Uyo Senatorial District.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter and implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools in Uyo Senatorial District, Akwa

Ibom State. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools.
2. Evaluate the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study and also achieve the stated objectives above.

1. What is the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools?
2. What is the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study and also achieve the stated objectives above.

1. There is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools.
2. There is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools.

Research Methods

The Expo-facto research design was adopted in the study.). Expo facto design was considered appropriate because the researcher will not manipulate the variable (gender) as it already existed (Kpolovie, 2016). This study was conducted in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State. The researchers used this area because of the observed poor academic performance by students in Mathematics. The population of the study consists of all the 346 Mathematics teachers in the public secondary schools, Uyo Senatorial District (source: Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board, 2023). The sample size for this study was one hundred (100) Mathematics teachers randomly drawn from 20 public secondary schools using simple random sampling technique through balloting.

The researcher developed instrument titled “Mathematics Teachers' Gender, Knowledge of Subject Matter and Implementation of Education Law Questionnaire (MTGKSMIELQ) was used for data collection. The instrument

had two sections (A and B). Section A had information on teachers' gender and Section B consisted of 20 items on Knowledge of subject matter (10 items) and implementation of Education Law (10 items). The instrument was scored using a four points rating scale as shown below: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point.

The instruments were subjected to content validity by three lecturers. Two lecturers from the Department of Psychological Foundations and one lecturer from Education Administration and Planning in Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The purpose of the study and the research questions were made available to them at the time of the validation. All the lecturers' comments were incorporated in the final copy of the instrument used to collect data for the study. To determine the internal consistency of the instruments, the researcher randomly selected 25 Mathematics teachers as respondents in a Department who was part of the population but are not part of the study sample to respond to the instrument. Data generated were subjected to inter-item analysis using, Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient Statistic for reliability coefficient determination. The reliability coefficients of 0.86 was obtained. These coefficients showed that the instrument was reliable. The researcher with the help of three well briefed research assistants administered the instruments to the selected respondents after seeking permission from the respective Principals through a letter of introduction from the researcher to carry out the study. Permission obtained allowed the subjects to respond to the items in the Instruments.

Data collected were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Independent t-test Statistics. The Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics were used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using Independent t-test Statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools?

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools.

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard deviation for the knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools based on Mathematics Teachers' gender

	Gender	n	Mean	SD.	p-cal.	p-crit.	Decision @ .05
Knowledge of subject matter	Male	57	34.45	7.43	.026	.05	S
	Female	43	21.37	4.29			

S= Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Computed by the Researcher using data from the respondents.

From the result in Table 1, it is revealed that the mean score of male Mathematics teachers' knowledge of subject matter is 34.45 and that of female Mathematics teachers is 21.37. This means that male Mathematics teachers had higher knowledge of subject matter than their female counterpart. With this observation, it implied that there is an influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools.

To determine whether the influence was significant, the p-calculated value for the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools is .029. This significant level is less than .05 alpha level in which the decision is based. This indicated that there is a significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools. Therefore, the formulated hypothesis was rejected.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools?

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools.

Table 2: Summary of Mean and Standard deviation for the implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools based on Mathematics Teachers' gender

	Gender	n	Mean	SD.	p-cal.	p-crit.	Decision @ .05
Implementation of Education Law	Male	57	31.24	8.24	.066	.05	NS
	Female	43	29.87	7.90			

NS= Not significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Computed by the Researcher using data from the respondents.

From the result in Table 2, it is revealed that the mean score of male Mathematics teachers' implementation of Education Law is 31.24 and that of female Mathematics teachers is 29.87. This means that male and female Mathematics teachers implement Education Law almost equally. With this observation, it implied that there is no influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools.

To determine whether the influence was significant, the p-calculated value for the influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools is .066. This significant level is greater than .05 alpha level in which the decision is based. This indicated that there is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools. Therefore, the formulated hypothesis was retained.

Discussion of the Findings

The result of the test of hypothesis one (H_{01}) revealed that there is a significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools. The findings also revealed that male Mathematics teachers had higher knowledge of subject matter than their female counterpart. The result could be attributed to the fact that any perceived differences in knowledge between male and female mathematics teachers are more likely to be related to individual variations in educational backgrounds, training, experience, and professional development opportunities. Additionally, societal factors, such as historical disparities in educational access and gender-based stereotypes, can contribute to differences in representation within the field. This can lead to a better understanding of the content and improved academic performance. The findings agreed with the findings of Akpan (2015) who reported that there is a significant influence of teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter.

The result of the test of hypothesis two (H_{02}) revealed that there is no significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools. The findings also revealed that both male and female Mathematics teachers implement Education Law in public secondary schools almost equally. The result could be attributed to the fact that the ability to implement education law is not inherently tied to gender but rather to factors such as legal knowledge, administrative skills, communication abilities, and leadership qualities. In addition, the

effectiveness of any teacher, regardless of gender, in implementing education law in a school setting is influenced by individual capabilities, experience, training, and commitment to staying informed about relevant legal matters. Lastly, success in implementing education law requires a combination of legal understanding, interpersonal skills, and an awareness of the educational context. The findings disagreed with the findings of Obilor (2020) who reported that teachers' gender influenced implementation of Education Law.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is hereby concluded that there is a significant influence of Mathematics Teachers' gender on knowledge of subject matter in public secondary schools. Mathematics Teachers' gender had no significant influence on implementation of Education Law in public secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusions reached, the following recommendations are made:

1. The government should invest in and promote professional development opportunities for mathematics teachers that are entirely gender-neutral.
2. The government should design and implement comprehensive training programs on education law that are entirely gender-neutral.

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